

IMPACT OF AFTER SCHOOL ACTIVITIES ON WEIGHT AMONG SCHOOL GOING CHILDREN

Dr. Meera Raman

Research Head, Department of Foods and Nutrition
Rathnavel Subramaniam College of Arts and Science
Trichy Road, Sulur, Coimbatore.

Abstract:

Obesity is increasing rapidly in developing countries due to the change in the life-style. Reduced physical activity and confinement to one place or long sitting hours are a part of the routine. This is mainly due to the technological development – computers and internet, mobiles, video games and television, reducing the physical activities of the children. Physical activity helps to burn calories. It also helps to reduce body fat and control weight, in turn prevents the occurrence of obesity. In this study, school going children (n=500) between the age group of 12 to 14 years were randomly chosen. Measurements taken were height and weight. BMI were deduced from height and weight. The after school activities of the selected subjects were evaluated. Data revealed very poor physical activities like outdoor games and more time were spent on sedentary activities like sitting and watching television, tuitions and playing mobile games. This was clearly indicated on analyzing BMI of the subjects. Prevalence of overweight was found to be 23% among boys and 26% among girls whereas the prevalence of obesity was 9% in boys and 6% in girls. Put together, over weight and obesity was noticed among 24% and 8% of the children respectively. The study suggest that the prevalence of overweight and obesity is markedly seen among school going children as the sedentary activities have crept in to the after school hours and it is imperative to create an awareness among school going children on the importance of physical activities like games and sports and exercise.

Keywords

Overweight, Obesity, After School Activity, Physical Activity, Body Mass Index, Sports and Games.

INTRODUCTION:

Obesity is a medical condition in which excess body fat has accumulated to the extent that it may have an adverse effect on health.^[1] The prevalence of overweight and obesity is a rapidly growing threat to public health due to the change in the life-style. Outcomes related to childhood obesity include hypertension, type 2 diabetes mellitus, dyslipidaemia, left ventricular hypertrophy, non-alcoholic steatohepatitis, obstructive Sleep apnoea, and orthopaedic and psychosocial problems.^{[2] [3] [4]}

Overweight and obesity are defined as abnormal or excessive fat accumulation that may impair health. Body Mass Index (BMI) is a simple index of weight-for-height that is commonly used to classify overweight and obesity. It is defined as a person's weight in kilograms divided by the square of his height in meters (kg/m²).

The WHO definition is:

- a BMI greater than or equal to 25 is overweight
- a BMI greater than or equal to 30 is obesity.

BMI provides the most useful population-level measure of overweight and obesity as it is the same for both.

Obesity is not just a disease of developed nations. Obesity levels in some lower-income and transitional countries are also high and the levels are increasing rapidly.^[5]

WHO states that the fundamental cause of obesity and overweight is an energy imbalance between calories consumed and calories expended. Globally, there has been:

- An increased intake of energy-dense foods that are high in fat; and
- A decrease in physical inactivity due to the increasingly sedentary nature of many forms of work, changing modes of transportation, and increasing urbanization.

Changes in dietary and physical activity patterns are often the result of environmental and societal changes associated with development and lack of supportive policies in sectors such as health, agriculture, transport, urban planning, environment, food processing, distribution, marketing and education.

Obesity and overweight among school going children are the common nutritional problems in developing countries including India. There is clear evidence of a demographic, epidemiological and nutrition transition in India that is fuelling the epidemic of chronic diseases and obesity, particularly in the urban areas.

Childhood obesity affects more than 15 percent of children, making it one of the common chronic disease of childhood. More and more children are being diagnosed soon and other with co-morbid conditions associated with obesity and morbid obesity.

Prevalence of overweight and obesity is more in school children in urban areas, and lack of physical activity is one of the main culprits. Regular physical activity is important for good health, and it is especially important to maintain a healthy weight and reduces the risk for many diseases. ^[6]

Objective:

- To assess the BMI of school going children.
- The study the prevalence of overweight and obesity among school going children in Coimbatore in relation to the after school activities.

Literature Review

The prevalence of overweight and obesity has increased substantially over the past three decades and is now considered as one of the most serious health challenges of the early 21st century. While the need for preventive action is increasingly recognized, policy implementation often occurs in a non-systematic, ad hoc manner. ^[7]

Lifestyle modification/behavior-based treatment interventions in youth with severe obesity have demonstrated modest improvement in body mass index status. To begin to address these challenges, the purposes of this scientific statement are to (1) provide justification for and recommend a standardized definition of severe obesity in children and adolescents; (2) raise awareness of this serious and growing problem by summarizing the current literature, associated health risks (immediate and long-term), and challenges and shortcomings of currently available treatment options; and (3) highlight areas in need of future research. ^[8]

The prevalence of obesity has risen so rapidly in recent decades that the World Health Organization has declared obesity a global epidemic. Changing physical activity and dietary habits are key to understanding obesity aetiology and are therefore important components in any obesity prevention and treatment strategies. ^[1]

Another major factor contributing to the childhood obesity epidemic is the increased sedentary lifestyle of children. School-aged children spend most of their day in school where their only activity comes during breaks or physical education classes. ^[9]

Numerous studies have shown that sedentary behaviors like watching television and playing computer games are associated with increased prevalence of obesity. ^{[10][11]}

Children in today's society show a decrease in overall physical activity. The growing use of computers, increased time watching television and decreased physical education in schools, all contribute to children and adolescents living a more sedentary lifestyle. "Screen time" activities such as watching television, gaming, texting, and playing on the computer require very little energy. They often take the place of healthy physical exercise. Also, children tend to crave unhealthy snack foods they see in TV ads. ^[12]

Only 50 percent of children of 12 to 21 years of age, regularly participate in rigorous physical activity, while 25 percent of children report no physical activity. The average child spends two hours a day watching television, but 26 percent of children watch at least four hours of television per day. ^[9]

Physical activity was associated with numerous health benefits. The dose-response relations observed in observational studies indicate that the more physical activity, the greater the health benefit. Results from experimental studies indicate that even modest amounts of physical activity can have health benefits in high-risk youngsters (e.g., obese). To achieve substantive health benefits, the physical activity should be of at least a moderate intensity. Vigorous intensity activities may provide even greater benefit. Aerobic-based activities had the greatest health benefit, other than for bone health, in which case high-impact weight bearing activities were required. ^[13]

Regular physical activity also appears to be critical specifically for the reduction of obesity related and other chronic diseases. Behavioral change is now recognized as an important component of any response to obesity and should be incorporated into treatment for weight loss and weight gain. Sedentary lifestyle and overweight are major public health, clinical, and economical problems in modern societies. The worldwide epidemic of excess weight is due to imbalance between physical activity and dietary energy intake. Sedentary lifestyle, unhealthy diet, and consequent overweight and obesity markedly increase the risk of cardiovascular diseases. Regular physical activity 45-60 min per day prevents unhealthy weight gain and obesity, whereas sedentary behaviors such as watching television promote them. Regular exercise can markedly reduce body weight and fat mass without dietary caloric restriction in overweight individuals. An increase in total energy expenditure appears to be the most important determinant of successful exercise-induced weight loss. The best long-term results may be achieved when physical activity produces an energy expenditure of at least 2,500 kcal/week. Yet, the optimal approach in weight reduction programs appears to be a combination of regular physical activity and caloric restriction. A minimum of 60 min, but most likely 80-90 min of moderate-intensity physical activity per day may be needed to avoid or limit weight regain in formerly overweight or obese individuals. Regular moderate intensity physical activity, a healthy diet, and avoiding unhealthy weight gain are effective and safe ways to prevent and treat cardiovascular diseases and to reduce premature mortality in all population groups. Although the efforts to promote cardiovascular health concern the whole population, particular attention should be paid to individuals who are physically inactive, have unhealthy diets or are prone to weight gain. They have the highest risk for worsening of the cardiovascular risk factor profile and for cardiovascular disease. To combat the epidemic of overweight and to improve cardiovascular health at a population level, it is important to develop strategies to increase habitual physical activity and to prevent overweight and obesity in collaboration with communities, families, schools, health care professionals, media and policymakers. ^[14]

The Body Mass Index (BMI) is the accepted standard measure of overweight and obesity for children two years of age and older. ^[15] BMI provides a guideline for weight in relation to height and is equal to the body weight (in kilograms) divided by the height (in meters) squared (table 1). Other measures of childhood obesity, including weight-for-height (which is particularly useful for the child younger than two years), measures of regional fat distribution (eg, waist circumference and waist-to-hip ratio), and the growth standards developed by the World Health Organization (WHO), are discussed separately. Unlike adults, children grow in height as well as weight. Thus, the norms for BMI in children vary with age and sex. BMI percentiles also can be determined. As children approach adulthood, the 85th and 95th percentile BMI for age and sex are approximately 25 and 30 kg/m², the thresholds for overweight and obesity, respectively. ^[16]

Methodology

The study included 500 school children in the age group of 11 to 14 years from urban and sub-urban areas. Consent to carry out the study was obtained from the school authorities. An interview schedule was designed to collect the data which was shown to the school authorities on obtaining the consent. 268 were boys and 232 were girls were selected for the study. The data collection included measurement of height and weight and to collect the after school activities of the students. The data were collected using an interview schedule. Height and weight were directly collected through direct physical examinations. Height and weight were measured using standard procedures. The height was measured using a non-stretchable measuring tape and weight was measured using a calibrated weighing balance. From these data, the BMI (kg/m²) was calculated for every student. The BMI of the students were then plotted on a percentile chart to identify the percentile range. From this, the students who were underweight, normal weight, overweight and obese were identified. This was further related to the after school activities of the students to study if there was a correlation between the after school activity and weight of the children.

Findings

The details of the data collected are consolidated and discussed below.

1. Selection of Subjects

School going students were randomly selected from schools. Both the genders were included. Both the genders were included. The details are given in Table - I and Figure -1.

Table – I : Age-wise, Gender-wise Distribution of the Selected School Going Children

S.No	Age in Years	Number of Boys	%	Number of Girls	%	Total Number of Students	%
1	12	102	38	67	29	169	34
2	13	86	32	88	38	174	35
3	14	80	30	77	33	157	31
TOTAL		268	100	232	100	500	100

The selected subjects were school going children between the age group of 12 to 14 years. Totally 268 boys and 232 girls participated in the study. Maximum number of students were of 13 years of age (n=174) followed by children of 12 years of age (n=169).

2. BMI of the Subjects

BMI of the selected children were calculated using the height and weight and they were plotted in the Percentile Chart for the age, depicted in Table - II and Figure - 2.

Table – II: BMI Category of the Selected School Going Children

S.NO	Gender	Strength Numbers	Normal	%	Over All %	Under Weight	%	Over All %	Over Weight	%	Over All %	Obese	%	Over All %
1	Girls	67	32	48	53	12	18	16	23	34	26	0	0	6
		88	46	52		11	13		22	25		9	10	
		77	44	57		13	17		15	19		5	6	
2	Boys	102	44	43	50	21	21	18	26	25	23	11	11	9
		86	48	56		14	16		19	22		5	6	
		80	42	53		14	18		17	21		7	9	
Total and %		500	256		51	85		17	122		24	37		7

On evaluating the BMI and marking them against the age for weight on the percentile chart, it was noted that 53 percent of the girls and 50 percent of the boys had a normal weight. The income level of all the families of the selected children were lower middle income group and low income group. This could be because the schools chosen for the study were situated in the sub-urban area. This added to the fact that there were underweight students indicated by 16 percent and 18 percent among girls and boys respectively.

Totally 51 percent maintained a normal weight and 17 percent were underweight. As the main aim of the study rested on over weight and obesity, it was surprising to note that both over weight and obesity were present among children. Higher figures represented the overweight category - 26 percent and 23 percent for girls and boys respectively. Obesity was noted more among the boys (9 percent) than the girls (6 percent). An overall percent indicated 7 percent being obese. Totally, 32 percent of the children in the study were overweight or obese. If this is left unchecked, there is all chance for the overweight children also to become obese.

3. Other Activities of the Subjects

The other activities were gathered as a part of the study which included sports, yoga and exercising. Table-III and Figure-3 give the details of these data.

Table – III : Other Activities of the Selected School Going Children

S. NO	Gender	Strength in Numbers	Other Activities															
			Sports						Yoga						Exercise			
			Yes	%	Over All %	No	%	Over All %	Yes	%	Over All %	No	%	Over All %	Yes	No	%	Over All %
1	Girls	67	27	40	19	40	60	81	18	27	30	49	73	70	NIL	67	100	100
		88	11	13		77	87		22	25		66	75		NIL	88	100	
		77	7	9		70	91		31	40		46	60		NIL	77	100	
2	Boys	102	60	59	38	42	41	62	21	21	18	81	79	82	NIL	102	100	100
		86	22	25		64	74		25	29		61	71		NIL	86	100	
		80	19	24		61	76		3	4		77	96		NIL	80	100	
Total and %		500	146		29	354		71	120		24	380		76	NIL	500		100

It can be noted from Table - III, that not all children participated in sports and games and yoga, which were optional at the schools. More boys (38 percent) participated in sports than girls (19 percent). It was the reverse in the case of yoga (boys 18 percent and girls 30 percent). However, in the weekly one hour for physical education, all the children involved themselves, as it was compulsory. Yoga was taught in the schools and those who enrolled themselves for classes did not practice daily at home. It was disheartening to note that no one involved themselves in regular exercising.

4. After School Activities of the Subjects :

Table – IV : After School Activities of the Selected School Going Children

S.NO	Gender	Strength in Numbers	Watching Television			Mobile/Video Games and Internet			Home Work and Tuition			Leisure Time with Friends (Talking)			Out Door Games		
			Up to 30 Minutes	30 to 60 Minutes	More than 60 Minutes	up to 30 Minutes	30 to 60 Minutes	More than 60 Minutes	Up to 30 Minutes	30 to 60 Minutes	More than 60 Minutes	Up to 30 Minutes	30 to 60 Minutes	More than 60 Minutes	Up to 30 Minutes	30 to 60 Minutes	More than 60 Minutes
1	Girls	67	5	25	37	28	5	0	6	29	32	13	18	21	7	0	0
		88	12	33	43	16	13	0	2	39	47	16	61	16	3	0	0
		77	8	12	57	11	8	0	7	27	43	7	43	37	0	0	0
	Total	232	25	70	137	55	26	0	15	95	122	36	122	74	10	0	0
	%	100	11	30	59	24	11	0	6	41	53	16	53	32	4	0	0
Over All %	232	100			35			100			100			4			100
2	Boys	102	27	54	21	7	34	61	11	41	50	19	41	42	5	0	7
		86	48	31	7	5	33	48	8	52	26	12	28	46	6	0	8
		80	45	31	4	11	36	33	5	34	41	23	33	24	5	4	11
	Total	268	120	116	32	23	103	142	24	127	117	54	102	112	16	4	26
	%	100	45	43	12	9	38	53	9	47	44	20	38	42	6	1	10
Over All %	268	100			100			100			100			17			
3	Boys and Girls Total	500	500			349			500			500			56		
	Boys and Girls %	100	100			70			100			100			11		

The main aim of the study was to correlate the weight of the selected children with their after school activities. The details are given in Table - IV and Figure - 4.

Table - IV indicates that all the girls involved in watching television, doing homework or attending tuitions and spending their leisure time with their friends and in the case of the boys all of them involved in watching television, doing homework or attending tuitions, playing with mobile/video games or spending time surfing on the internet and spending leisure time with their friends talking.

The girls who involved themselves in outdoor games (4 percent) played tennicoit or shuttle and mentioned that they were generally not permitted to go nearby to playgrounds and to friends places to play and their surrounding were not much conducive to play out. The boys (17 percent) on the other hand played cricket and to meet their friends and to play they mostly went by cycle. Invariably, these boys went to play, meet friends, to school and back home by cycling.

More time was spent on watching television for more than one hour by girls (59 percent) than boys (12 percent). A similar scenario was noticed for doing homework or tuitions indicated by 53 percent among girls and 44 percent among boys. No girl played mobile or video games more than one hour as they preferred to watch television whereas, 53 percent of the boys involved in playing mobile or video games or surfing on the internet for more than one hour. The remaining time was spent for refreshing, consumption of snacks, dinner and talking with the family members. It was also noted from the children felt that the time spent with the family was very less as in most cases both the parents were working or the parents were also engaged with the television and computers.

Limitations/scope for future work

1. To study in private and international schools in the urban areas.
2. To study the food pattern and relate to it with the physical activity and to correlate them with the weight of the school going children.

Conclusion

It could be concluded that the after school activities of the children were mainly sedentary in nature. Very little time by very few children was spent on outdoor games. This trend will lead to overweight and obese children in the society, further leading to various health disorders. Hence, an emergency call is required to assess prevalence of overweight and obesity among children and create an awareness on food habits and after school activities among children, school authorities and parents to curb the occurrence of overweight and obese children in our nation.

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ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Dr. MEERA RAMAN is a Associate Professor and Research Head in the Department of Foods and Nutrition at Rathnavel Subramaniam College of Arts & Science, Suler, Coimbatore. Her Doctoral programme was on “**Tube Feeding Formulae**” from Bharathiar University, Coimbatore. Her area of experience is Clinical Nutrition and Food Processing. She has eighteen year of service in teaching in higher education and in research.